

ANALYSIS OF THE ATTITUDE OF URBAN AND RURAL HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS TOWARDS PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to compare the attitude of urban and rural high school students towards physical education. One hundred high school male students were selected to serve as subjects from both urban and rural schools. Five schools from Lucknow city (urban) and five schools from rural areas around Lucknow were chosen for the study. Ten students were randomly reelected from each school. The average age of the subjects was 15 years. Edgington high school attitude scale was employed to assess the attitude of urban and rural high school students towards physical education. To compare the attitude of urban and rural students towards physical education 't' test was employed. The level of significance chosen was .05. When urban and rural high school students, were compared it was found that urban school boys studying in Lucknow city had favorable attitude towards physical education. The mean score of urban student was significantly higher than rural student at .05 level of confidence.

Keywords: urban and rural high school students, attitude towards physical education

1. Introduction

Education is the process by which the individual is shaped to fit into the society and which maintains and advances the social order.

Physical education has a vital role to play as an integral part of general education which aims at enabling an individual to live an enriched and abundant life in ever changing world. Change is necessary because our society is changing our students are changing and our resources are changing. If we are to meet the demands of helping

young people learn to live effectively in today's world and be capable of change, then we need to recognize deterrents of those goals that exists within our collective attitude.

The attitude of the students towards physical education has a significant role to play in its development. Attitude arises out of experiences and therefore the school which seeks to develop specific attitude among its pupil must provide opportunities for relevant experiences. The development of healthy favorable attitude is itself a phase of education, for they facilitate learning and serve as a cause for further motivation.

2. Method

Five schools from Lucknow city and Five from rural areas around Lucknow, were chosen for the study. Ten male students from high school class of each chosen school were randomly selected for the study. Edgington attitude scale comprising of 66 statements was employed on randomly selected 100 school boys to study their attitude towards physical education. Out of those 100 students, 50 students each were taken from urban and rural schools in and around Lucknow city.

The criterion measure chosen for the study were the obtained scores from each student measured by Edgington attitude scale. According to norms, scores above 264 would indicate an attitude on the favorable side and score below 264 indicate an attitude on the unfavorable side. To decide the positive and negative attitudes of the subjects towards physical education norm of the questionnaire was referred and to decide the difference in the attitudes of urban and rural students towards physical education 't' test was employed. The level of significance was set at .05.

3. Findings

To compare urban and rural school boys with regard to their attitude towards physical education, their mean values were referred with the prescribed norms on Edgington scale and to determine the significance of difference between them 't' test was employed. Following table represents the findings.

Table 1: Comparison & Significance of Difference of Mean Value of Urban and Rural School Boys on Their Attitude towards Physical Education

Group	Mean	SD Mean difference	't' ratio	Norms
Urban Student	272.60	17.40	33.10	10.03*264
Rural Student	239.50	15.91		

*Significant at .05 level of confidence.

't' value required to be significant at .05 level with 98 degree of freedom is 1.98.

The analysis of data from table -1 reveal that the mean value of 272.60 obtained by urban students is higher than the prescribed value of 264 on Edington scale, whereas the mean value of 239.50 obtained by rural students is lower than the required value.

The analysis of data also shows that urban school boys studying in Lucknow city have significantly higher favorable attitude towards physical education, then those of rural school boys studying around Lucknow as the obtained 't' value 10.03 is higher than that of required value of 1.98 at .05 level of confidence.

4. Discussion of findings

The analysis of data from Table 1 reveals that the urban school boys had favorable attitude towards physical education. Whereas, rural students do not have a favorable attitude towards physical education. This may be attributed to the fact that the urban school boys studying in Lucknow city are aware of the values of physical education program. The sport related environment of Lucknow city might also be contributing towards their favorable attitude towards physical education.

The analysis of data also reveal that the urban school boys have significantly more favorable attitude towards physical education, then those of rural students studying around Lucknow. It may be due to the fact that urban school boys have more opportunity to participate in sound physical education program as there is no scarcity of funds, facility, equipment and leadership for running physical education program properly. On the other hand, the program of physical education is either does not exist or is not as sound in schools of rural areas around Lucknow as there is a paucity of funds, facilities equipment and leadership to run the physical education program efficiently.

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